

Rice-based cropping systems

Irrigated sunflower in rice fallows of Konkan

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In Konkan, a humid area with heavy rainfall, rice is the main crop in the monsoon season (Jun-Sep). After rice is harvested, most fields remain fallow. As more irrigation projects are constructed, potential for cropping in the rice fallow increases.

We evaluated sunflower after rice and sought to determine the appropriate level of N application on three sunflower varieties (EC68413, EC68414, and EC69874). N levels were 40, 60, and 80 kg N/ha. Treatments were in three replications. Experiments began in Nov 1973, 1974, and 1975 after rice harvest. Fields were on

Effect of nitrogen levels 40, 60, 80 kg/ha, on mean yield of sunflower varieties planted after rice, Konkan, India.

Year	Yield (t/ha)									CD at 5%
	EC68413			EC68414			EC69874			
	40	60	80	40	60	80	40	60	80	
1973-74	1.8	2.0	2.1	1.8	2.1	2.1	1.2	1.7	1.8	NS
1974-75	1.4	1.5	1.3	1.6	2.1	2.2	1.7	1.2	1.0	NS
1975-76	1.3	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.4	1.3	1.4	1.4	1.7	NS
Pooled mean		1.7			1.9			1.4		0.18

Interaction CD at 5% 0.3

irrigated laterite soils, which had high N and K and medium P content. Sunflower was sown at 60- × 30-cm spacing at 10 kg seed/ha. Plants were thinned to 1/hill. P at 11 kg/ha was applied basally at sowing. N was applied in equal splits at sowing and 1 mo later. The crop was irrigated

every 10-12 d and received 8 irrigations.

Results from 3 yr showed that EC68414 yielded significantly more than the other varieties. Nitrogen levels did not produce significantly different yields, but the interaction between N and varieties was significant (see table). □

Announcements

Yoshida dies

Dr. Shouichi Yoshida, principal scientist and head of the IRRI Plant Physiology Department, died 23 Jan 1984 in Tokyo, Japan, after an extended illness. He was 53.

Yoshida earned his BS degree in agricultural chemistry in 1954 and the D Agr in soil science and plant nutrition in 1964, both from the University of Hokkaido. He joined the IRRI staff in 1966. Yoshida's primary research interests were in mineral nutrition, crop physiology, and environmental influence on the rice crop.

He made significant contributions to rice science with his work on high temperature-induced spikelet fertility, zinc deficiency research that led to the recognition of zinc as the third most important nutrient for rice, and physiological studies on the potential produc-

tivity of rice in the tropics and in temperate areas.

During his professional career Yoshida authored or coauthored more than 70 scientific and technical publications. He wrote the widely used *Laboratory manual for physiological studies of rice*. His *Fundamentals of rice crop science*, a 1981 IRRI book, is being translated into Chinese, Spanish, and Vietnamese. □

Grain processing losses bibliography

The Tropical Development and Research Institute (TDRI) has published the *Grain processing losses bibliography, supplement 1 to G117*, covering combine harvesting, threshing, hulling, milling, and grinding, and excluding storage. For further information contact TDRI, 127 Clerkenwell Road, London, EC 1R 5 DB UK. □

Miah receives gold medal

S. A. Miah, head of the Plant Pathology Department of the Bangladesh Rice Research Institute, was awarded a presidential gold medal by the Government of Bangladesh for his contribution to rice research and development. Miah was a senior research fellow at IRRI in 1977-78. □